

SEMANTIC GROUPINGS OF ENGLISH LEXICON

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Abstract: This article analyzes a lexical field whose members are related by meaning, references or use. Also, its types that can help us know to use our vocabulary more cohesively. That is very useful for learners of any kind of language.

Key words: semantic, lexico-semantic, parts, range, vocabulary, order, synonym, words, antonyms, hyponym, hyponym, metonym, meanings

When someone tells you "Oh, outside is very cool" you will obviously think about cold weather, but what about when someone tells you that you look cool. How would you think? Could you imagine it as a compliment? Ability to understand and differ meanings can be acquired thanks to lexical branch lexical semantic relations. This branch will be useful for learners of certain language both to use a range variety of vocabulary and to be aware of their meanings, which helps to be more cohesive and use words confidently.

Let's firstly get acquainted with semantics. Semantics is the study of meaning in terms of words, phrases, and sentences. It's focused on meaning rather than how it is used in context.

There lexical semantics deal with the study of words. Lexical relations have to do with the meaning of words and their relationship with one another. There are six types of relations:

1. Synonym
2. Antonym
3. Homonyms
4. Polysemy

5. Hyponymy

6. Metonymy

1. Synonyms are the words that have the same meaning, e.g big-huge-large. However, to replace a word with its synonyms must consider factors including context, because synonym doesn't mean total sameness and some synonyms can't be replaced it wherever you want. For this reason synonyms are divided into two groups:

a. Absolute synonyms. They are the words that can be replaced in all context, e.g insect -bug.

b. Partial synonyms, they have close meaning but not the same, there learners should be attentive and consider factors given above. For example the words big - gigantic

2. Antonyms are the words that have opposite meaning, e.g white-black. There are three groups of antonyms:

a. Gradable antonyms are described so **having opposite at each end** of spectrum, but has a progression of stages. For example, cold-hot and there **between them** they have **a some** kind of mixture of cold and **hot that** is warm.

B. Complementary (non- gradable) there words have **absolute opposite meaning without progression**. For instance, yes-no.

C. Reverse antonyms, as its **name it** has a **reverse relation**, e.g night-day

3. Hyponymy- happens when the meaning of one word included to the another. It can be called as hierarchical relationship. There are 3 types of hyponymy.

A. Hypernym- which is general term for words.

B. Hyponym- more specific.

C. Co-hyponyms – are the words that are in the same level. For example,

HYPERNYM: ANIMAL

Hyponym: FISH Mammal

Salmon Trout sheep wolf

4. Homonym- are the words that have the same pronunciation and spelling, but have different meaning, e.g bat (animal) – bat (thing used for hittingball). There should be **mentioned homonym's relative homophone**, which has different spelling but the same **pronunciation as** in **example right-write**

5. Polysemy-happens when one word has several meanings. Light- not heavy , color

6. Metonym-is a word that **replaces original** word. There the word must be associated with **these word. For example**, 'Can you **give me** a hand to **finish my project**?'. There **hand refers** to the word 'help'.

From the article we can see how studying these types will have a great influence not only in our using of vocabulary but also to understand natives correctly. Lexical semantics also create reference points for words making it more colorful. The relationships between words also show us how it is we think about the world. The very fact that we view “happy” as the opposite of “sad” tells us something about human experience.

References

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